

The Searching for Analyzing the GDP per capita variation with Chinese Provinces Comparison Sustainably through Observing Statistic Data

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ABSTRACT: The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained a low economy situation but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously special by those scientist, senior engineer, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into

realizing new-quality productivity producing a certain effectiveness to GDP enhancement as last. In the meantime, the new-high-technology product will be formed accordingly that can create the industrial chains to support the high-knowledge skill transformed into the more comprehensive and complicated product for the sake of serving our citizen with modernization. The emerging technology would be driven the new energy force that includes the low -carbon and low-contamination electricity generator which may form the new quality productivity protected our earth from carbon-oxide and nitric-oxide etc. release. So that some the high-tech products would aware that the transformation and positively prepare the futural product producing and application. Thereby, the nation's GDP will reflect the whole economy special in new high-tech-field maker and products will play a significant influence on that value increasement and control the y-y value under our consideration.

Keywords: *Searching for; analyzing; GDP per capita variation for Chinese Provinces; by sustainably observing.*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the detail discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new

quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence) ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique

instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~22]

2. Discussions

The GDP per capita variation for Chinese Provinces

The GDP per capita variation for Korea & Chinese cities would show 1,770~388 dollars by Korea & Shanghai provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 1 expressed the Korea forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 0.5%~6% respectively exhibited the Shanghai city forwards step.

Figure 1 The GDP per capita variation for Korea & Chinese ones. [1]

The GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones would show 1,770~388 dollars by Beijing & Tianjin provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 2 expressed the Beijing forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 10% both exhibited their ones forwards step.

Figure 2 The GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones I. [1]

The GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones would show 110~95 dollars by Liaoning & Heilongjiang provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 3 expressed their forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 10%~13% respectively exhibited their ones forwards step.

Figure 3 The GDP per capita variation for Chinese provinces II. [1]

The GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones would show 78~70 dollars by Jiangsu & Guangdong provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 4 expressed their forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 8%~20% respectively exhibited the Guangdong one forwards step.

Figure 4 The GDP per capita variation for Chinese provinces III. [1]

The GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones would show 70~66 dollars by Xizang & Qinghai provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 5 expressed their

forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 20%~3% respectively exhibited the Xizang forwards step.

Figure 5 The GDP per capita variation for Korea & Chinese provinces IV. [1]

At the end, the GDP per capita variation for Chinese ones would show 65~69 dollars by Shanxi & Zhejiang provinces accordingly in 1980 in light of Figure 6 expressed their forwards economy level. The y-y value might attain 5%~15% respectively exhibited the Zhejiang forwards step.

Figure 6 The GDP per capita variation for Korea & Chinese provinces V. [1]

Summarily, the enhancing GDP behaviors will be meaning regulating the one for matching new dynamic balance according to exhibiting new tendency like War, disease and political fringe conflict which affect our life for a certain economic

developing degree. So that the judgement may be according to the met actual situation making a corresponding method like increasing & decreasing this year or next one anticipating value so as to alleviate the nation burdens. Thereby, the fitting value may be satisfying the domestic consumption demands in order to rise up the positive consumption that will help us to go through the difficult situation when the risk happen. On the other side, the foreign trade will be encouraged so that the exportation win the importation for the sake of acquiring corresponding foreign reservation that is to be essential in critical period like when we buy some necessary goods abroad like military and defence weapon and equipment when we meet difficulty. Presently the high-technique product like drones and low air economy demands us to wield more powerful role in delivering the package and taking-out brisker and quicker that enable form the automatic and artificial intelligence service in big cities completed by robots from the reserve-box to each floor offices directly. So we look at the convenience and security. We should continuously to search for the new automatic & artificial intelligence robot work function special in the humanoid ones.

3. Conclusions

The GDP can make sure that one nation's economy status within one year which defines that year economy activity and consumption situation, so that it may reflect directly the nation's citizens satisfactory degree through investigating Q&A (question & answer) situation etc. polled survey. Therefore, the fit value for last year and next year will be important to each people so that we can make a plan to be journey overseas and spend some money on favorite goods. All of them can be done under a prosperous economy environment and support. At the same time, the nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy

developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decrease through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained a low economy situation but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously special by those scientist, senior engineer, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into realizing new-quality productivity producing a certain effectiveness to GDP enhancement as last. In the meantime, the new-high-technology product will be formed accordingly that can create the industrial chains to support the high-knowledge skill transformed into the more comprehensive and complicated product for the sake of serving our citizen with modernization. The emerging technology would be driven the new energy force that includes the low -carbon and low-contamination electricity generator which may form the new quality productivity protected our earth from carbon-oxide and nitric-oxide etc. release. So that some the high-tech products would aware that the transformation and positively prepare the futural product producing and application. Thereby, the nations GDP will reflect the whole economy special in new high-tech-field maker and products will play a significant influence on that value increasement and control the y-y value under our consideration.

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